

seeds; training farmers, farm women, rural youth, and science graduates; organizing demonstrations in F_1 commercial seed production; popularizing hybrid rice technology through extension services; and producing multimedia training materials on hybrid rice technology. The important lesson we learned was that for each location and season, we needed to determine the seeding interval for the parental lines. During the past three seasons (1995-96), hybrid rice seed

production was carried out on 164 ha in farmers' fields. A total yield of 195 t of hybrid seeds was produced and supplied to various companies and individual farmers. This seed was enough for the commercial production of hybrid rice on 9,750 ha. During the 1996 wet season, hybrid rice seed production was carried out on 90 ha.

Training progressive farmers, youth, and farm women in hybrid rice seed production and F_1 commercial cultivation promotes hybrid rice cultivation

and increases rice yields. Training was organized in hybrid rice seed production for various categories of clients—farmers, farm women, farm youth, extension officers, and representatives of seed companies. More than 33,400 man-days of training were imparted during 1995-96. With the assistance of the United Nations Development Programme, this KVK organized a large-scale training program for farm women. ■

Socioeconomic impact

Economics of hybrid rice seed production in India

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Input-output data on hybrid seed production were obtained from seed growers' farms under private companies and a nongovernment organization (KVK, Gaddipally, Andhra Pradesh) from 1992-93 to 1994-95. Using these data, we studied the cost-return profile of F_1 seed production. The F_1 seed yield was only 560 kg ha⁻¹ when it was produced for the first time in 1992-93, but it increased to 1,385 kg ha⁻¹ in 1994-95. The average total cost of

F_1 seed production was Rs 23,840 ha⁻¹. Costs involved 45% for labor, 24% for manure and fertilizers, and 8% for gibberellic acid. The cost of 1 kg of seed produced dropped from Rs 33 (US\$0.92) in 1992-93 to Rs 17 (US\$0.48) during 1994-95, primarily because of increased yield. Because hybrid rice seed production is labor-intensive, 280-300 additional man-days of employment could be generated in the rural area, especially for women. In addition, gross and net returns to F_1 seed production are Rs 42,710 (US\$1,186) and Rs 18,870 (US\$524) ha⁻¹, respectively, at Rs 25 (US\$0.69) as the procurement price kg⁻¹. At the rate of the procurement price paid to seed growers by the seed industry, however, the computed

economically viable threshold seed yield was 1,900 kg ha⁻¹. If F_1 seed production is to be made economically viable to seed growers at 1,385 kg ha⁻¹ of seed yield, the procurement price should be Rs 34 (US\$0.95) kg⁻¹. The ratio of seed (F_1) area to commercial cultivation area of hybrid rice is estimated at 1:37.6. Thus, close to 53,000 ha are needed for an F_1 seed production program to meet the seed requirement of 2 million ha under hybrid rice by the year 2000. Our results stress the need to further improve F_1 seed yields. We also need to formulate an incentive-oriented and forward-contract base price policy for F_1 seed to induce seed growers to produce the required hybrid rice seed. ■

Impact of hybrid rice on India's food economy: implications and policy issues

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Basic data from the literature on the nature and impact of the adoption of hybrid rice in China and experiences in other research centers were gathered. Additional supporting data were collected from farmers' fields in the major rice-growing states in India

where rice hybrids were released recently. All these data formed the basis for this study. Hybrid rice outyields existing conventional high-yielding varieties by 1-2 t ha⁻¹ in irrigated environments. The adoption of hybrid rice would shift the production function farther upward and the increased rice output in irrigated areas would result in a higher domestic supply. In the short run, this could lead to a further widening of the income inequalities between irrigated and unirrigated regions. In addition, hybrid rice would benefit large farmers, who are early adopters with an ability to

purchase costly hybrid rice seed every crop season. A long-term use of this technology, however, would benefit the entire rice-farming community and urban population as well. Hybrid rice technology would generate a more marketable surplus. As a consequence, higher domestic prices of rice would be prevented in the consumer market, which would benefit urban consumers, especially low and middle class groups. Hybrid rice would also add to central buffer stocks and increase the supply of rice through the public distribution system at cheaper prices. Because hybrid rice technology is labor-

intensive, particularly seed production, it generates additional employment opportunities, especially for women (nearly 280-300 man-days ha⁻¹) in rural India. Thus, the purchasing power of landless labor would increase through an increase in earnings from labor.

Evidence from China, a centrally planned economy, shows that direct government intervention through incentive policies, apart from yield advantage, played a significant role in popularizing hybrid rice on a large

scale. These policies involved an incentive output price for hybrid rice grains despite poor grain quality, on a par with that of other popular varieties; the assured procurement of surplus output at an incentive price; a supply of hybrid seed free of cost during the initial stage; a supply of other inputs such as fertilizer at concessional rates for farmers who adopt hybrid rice; and a well-organized seed production system. Experiences in the United States and Japan market economies

during the 1980s, however, indicate that farmers did not accept hybrid rice because of its poor grain quality. Now India has emerged as the second country after China, in the development and release of high-yielding rice hybrids. The fixing of a support price for hybrid rice grains by the government, on a par with that of popular varieties, would certainly induce rice farmers in irrigated regions to adopt hybrid rice on a large scale. ■